

Fast Greedy Selection Hyper-heuristics

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Abstract. Selection hyper-heuristics (HHs) are self-adaptive algorithms that select from a pre-defined set of low-level heuristics which one to apply at each decision point of the optimisation process. The simple Greedy selection HH works by running all heuristics at the same time and accepting the action from the heuristic that produces the largest improvement in the solution quality. Recent analyses have shown that the performance of the Greedy HH is essentially equivalent to one that chooses heuristics uniformly at random in each iteration, and that a Generalised Greedy HH (GG) that applies the greedily chosen heuristic for an exploitation period of $\tau > 0$ iterations can outperform its low-level heuristics when acting on their own for the LEADINGONES benchmark function, if GG is equipped with two operators. We first prove that the best runtime achievable by GG using two operators is not optimal. Furthermore, we show that GG is ineffective because its performance degrades with the increase of the size of the heuristic set it can select from. To overcome this limitation, we improve the HH by allowing it to apply the greedily chosen heuristic in a gradient descent manner. The new Fast Greedy HH is shown to have *optimal* performance on the LEADINGONES benchmark function for an arbitrary number of low-level heuristics. The rigorous theoretical results are complemented with an experimental analysis showing the improved performance in practice of the Fast Greedy HH over previously studied HHs for the function.

Keywords: Hyper-heuristics · Runtime Analysis · Greedy Algorithms.

1 Introduction

Randomised search heuristics have been applied successfully to a number of real world optimisation problems. Despite this, it is difficult to decide which heuristic is a good choice for a given optimisation problem. Furthermore, different heuristics may have better performance at different stages of the optimisation process. The aim of the field of hyper-heuristics (HHs) is to overcome these difficulties by automatically evolving the search heuristic for the problem at hand, rather than applying a tedious trial-and-error algorithm selection and parameter optimisation approach. The overall goal is to achieve a more generally

applicable system by automating the design and the tuning of the heuristic and parameters for the optimisation problem [7].

HHs have been successfully applied to a number of NP-hard optimisation problems, including scheduling [9, 10, 21], timetabling [35], vehicle routing [4], cutting and packing [31]. Yet, their theoretical understanding is still limited.

Recent years have witnessed significant advances in the theoretical analysis of selection HHs. In particular, time complexity analyses have shed light onto their behaviour and performance [2, 25, 3, 36, 29, 17, 30, 32, 5, 18, 14, 34]. The first analysis of selection HHs was conducted by Alanazi and Lehre [2] who analysed four basic selection HHs from the literature, namely the Simple Random HH, Random Gradient HH, Permutation HH, and Greedy HH [9, 10], and showed that they all have the same asymptotic performance for the LEADINGONES benchmark function when equipped with a low-level heuristic set H consisting of two random local search operators with different neighbourhood sizes (called 1BITFLIP and 2BITFLIP, which respectively flip one bit and two bits with replacement). Lissovoi et al. [29] made this result concrete by proving that all four HHs optimise LEADINGONES in the same expected runtime up to lower order terms (i.e., $(1 + o(1)) \cdot ((\ln 3)/2)n^2 \approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.54931n^2$). This result shed light on the fact that the potentially smarter HHs such as the Random Gradient HH and the Greedy HH do not gain any advantage from choosing the most appropriate operator for the next step compared to simply selecting an operator uniformly at random. While the result was provided for the LEADINGONES benchmark function, the insight applies to any *perturbative* optimisation problem, where a complete candidate solution is repeatedly modified.

The idea behind these two HHs is to exploit operators that have a higher probability of identifying improvements at the current stage of the process. However, in a perturbative problem, the expected time for any unbiased operator to identify an improvement is generally considerably larger than 1. Thus re-applying even the currently best operator available only once after it has found a better solution will not allow the HH to appreciate its effectiveness, and hence will not speed up the optimisation process compared to selecting operators uniformly at random (i.e., it will have the same performance as the Simple Random HH).

Lissovoi et al. [28] used this insight to design appropriate HHs for perturbative problems, which they respectively called the *Generalised Random Gradient* (GRG) HH and *Generalised Greedy* (GG) HH. Rather than re-applying a successful operator for just one step, they introduced a parameter τ that defines the time period that a successful low-level heuristic is run for before deciding whether it should be applied again or not. They then proved that if the learning period is set appropriately i.e., $\tau = \omega(n)$ and roughly $\tau = \mathcal{O}(n \ln n)$, then the GRG HH, equipped with any constant (i.e., $k = \mathcal{O}(1)$) number of Randomised Local Search low-level heuristics (RLS $_i$ - i.e., flip exactly i bits chosen without replacement), optimises the LEADINGONES function in the optimal runtime achievable with its set of operators up to lower order terms. We call such a performance *optimal* for the HH, because it is the best that can be hoped for with the available low-level heuristics. If equipped with the first segment of 18 opera-

tors, i.e., $H = \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_{18}\}$, then the GRG HH optimises LEADINGONES already in expected time $\approx 0.388n^2$, which is the best possible expected runtime for any (1+1) black box algorithm [12, 19]. The analysis of the GRG HH was later extended to other benchmark functions and led to the design of improved theory-driven random gradient HHs [27, 17, 32].

Concerning the GG HH, however, the analysis of Lissovoi et al. [28] is inconclusive. They analysed GG equipped with two low level heuristics $H = \{\text{1BITFLIP}, \text{2BITFLIP}\}$, using a linear exploitation period τ for the greedily chosen operators for LEADINGONES. They provided an upper bound on the expected runtime that is smaller than the $0.5n^2$ expected runtime of 1BITFLIP (i.e., the best low level heuristic) and of the $\approx 0.549n^2$ of the original Greedy HH, but is larger than the best possible expected runtime of $\approx 0.423n^2$, which is achieved by the GRG HH [29]. In particular, from the results it is unclear whether the bound is tight and how GG performs when equipped with a larger number of low-level heuristics.

Our first result is that the best possible expected runtime of GG with the heuristic set $H = \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ for LEADINGONES is $\approx 0.478n^2$, which is achieved using a super-linear exploitation period τ and is indeed slower than that of GRG. Furthermore, we show that increasing the size of the low-level heuristic set H degrades the performance, even though the best possible expected runtime decreases with the size of H . This is in contrast with the GRG HH, which always has optimal performance for LEADINGONES up to lower order terms, independent of the amount ($k = \mathcal{O}(1)$) of low-level heuristics available [29].

Thus, to aid the design of efficient greedy HH, we propose a Fast Greedy (FG) HH that combines the decision stage of the Greedy HH to select the most promising low-level heuristic for the current stage of the optimisation process, and the effective exploitation stage of the GRG HH, thus it continues to re-use the currently chosen heuristic in a random gradient style so long as it identifies an improvement within the *exploitation period* τ .

We prove that FG equipped with an arbitrary number of low-level heuristics indeed optimises LEADINGONES in the best possible expected runtime using its available heuristics and is more robust to the exploitation period τ than the GRG HH. In particular, FG reaches optimal performance with smaller exploitation periods. An experimental analysis confirms that FG outperforms GRG in practice.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. In Section 2 we introduce the LEADINGONES benchmark function and the Greedy and Generalised Greedy HHs. In Sections 3-4 we analyse the Generalised Greedy with heuristic sets of sizes 2 and larger respectively, and in Section 5 we analyse the Fast Greedy HH. We present some supplementary experiments in Section 7. We conclude the paper with some discussions on some natural extensions of this work.

Algorithm 1 Greedy Hyper-heuristic [9, 2]

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1: Choose  $x \in S$  uniformly at random
2: while stopping conditions not satisfied do
3:    $\forall h \in H$ , apply  $h(x)$ ;
4:    $f(h'(x)) := \max_{h \in H} \{f(h(x))\}$ .
5:   if  $f(h'(x)) > f(x)$  then
6:      $x \leftarrow h'(x)$ 

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2 Preliminaries

2.1 Greedy Hyper-heuristic Methodologies

Let S be a finite search space, H a set of low-level heuristics and $f : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ a cost function. Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode representation for the simple Greedy selection HH as used in previous work [9, 2]. Note that all heuristics are applied independently to the current solution, and the one that yields the largest improvement is selected. If no heuristics lead to an improvement, this process is repeated. The Greedy HH has the same performance for LEADINGONES (when choosing between the set of low-level heuristics $H = \{1\text{BITFLIP}, 2\text{BITFLIP}\}$) as the Simple Random HH, which selects a low-level heuristic at random in each iteration [29]. By making a heuristic selection decision in every iteration without taking past performance into account, the Greedy HH does not make efficient use of the information learnt in the previous decision stage.

Thus, Lissovoi et al. [28] introduced the Generalised Greedy (GG) HH to exploit the greedily chosen heuristic for a certain amount of time. The algorithm works as follows. All low-level heuristics in the set H are tested on the same candidate solution until an improvement is found (*Decision Stage*). The largest improvement (chosen uniformly at random if there are multiple ones) is then accepted and the corresponding operator is run for a fixed period of time τ (*Exploitation Stage*). The pseudocode for GG is shown in Algorithm 2.

Lissovoi et al. [28] proved that using $H = \{1\text{BITFLIP}, 2\text{BITFLIP}\}$ and a linear exploitation period, GG is faster for LEADINGONES than its lower level heuristics applied in isolation and compared to the original Greedy hyper-heuristic. Yet the bound provided was larger than the optimal possible expected runtime achievable for the function (i.e., $\approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.42329n^2$) with the heuristic set H , which instead is met by GRG [29]. We first generalise this result and show that the best runtime achievable by GG is $\approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.47797n^2$ (versus $\approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.54931n^2$ of the simple Greedy HH) which is obtained for any super-linear exploitation period $\tau = \omega(n) \cap o(n^2)$. However, we then show that the performance of GG degrades as the number of heuristics $|H|$ increases.

With the aim of developing more effective greedy HHs, we propose to modify the GG heuristic to combine the benefits of both the greedy selection of low level heuristics and the exploitation phase of random gradient HHs [27, 29]. Thus, we implement a gradient-style exploitation of the greedily chosen heuristic into the GG framework. The resulting Fast Greedy (FG) HH, combines the Decision

Algorithm 2 Generalised Greedy Hyper-Heuristic

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1: Choose  $x \in S$  uniformly at random
2: while stopping conditions not satisfied do
  // Decision Stage
3:  $\forall h \in H$ , apply  $h(x)$  repeatedly until some  $h'$  has  $f(h'(x)) > f(x)$ . If there is
   more than one improvement, take the  $h'$  which produced the largest (ties broken
   at random).
  // Exploitation Stage
4:  $c_t \leftarrow 0$ 
5: while  $c_t < \tau$  do
6:    $c_t \leftarrow c_t + 1$ ;  $x' \leftarrow h'(x)$ 
7:   if  $f(x') > f(x)$  then
8:      $x \leftarrow x'$ 

```

Algorithm 3 Fast Greedy Hyper-Heuristic

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1: Choose  $x \in S$  uniformly at random
2: while stopping conditions not satisfied do
  // Decision Stage
3:  $\forall h \in H$ , apply  $h(x)$  repeatedly until some  $h'$  has  $f(h'(x)) > f(x)$ . If there is
   more than one improvement take the  $h'$  which produced the largest (ties broken at
   random).
  // Exploitation Stage
4:  $c_t \leftarrow 0$ 
5: while  $c_t < \tau$  do
6:    $c_t \leftarrow c_t + 1$ ;  $x' \leftarrow h'(x)$ 
7:   if  $f(x') > f(x)$  then
8:      $c_t \leftarrow 0$ ,  $x \leftarrow x'$ 

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Stage of GG (i.e., where all operators are run in parallel and the first to make a fitness improvement is chosen) and uses this operator in a gradient-based Exploitation Stage like the one employed by GRG [29] (i.e., the chosen operator is run for a period of τ steps and each fitness improvement resets the period of τ , thus it is used as long as it is successful). The idea is to combine the learning aspects of the two HHs to create a more advanced HH that chooses the currently best heuristic and keeps using it so long as it is successful. The pseudocode for FG is shown in Algorithm 3. We will show that FG equipped with an arbitrary number of randomised local search heuristics, $H_k := \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_k\}$, has optimal expected runtime for the standard LEADINGONES benchmark and uses shorter exploitation periods τ than GRG.

2.2 The LeadingOnes Benchmark Function

The $\text{LEADINGONES}(x) := \sum_{i=1}^n \prod_{j=1}^i x_j$ benchmark function counts the number of consecutive one-bits in a bit string before the first zero-bit.

Its unary unbiased black box complexity is $\Theta(n^2)$ [26], a bound which is matched by the performance of simple well studied heuristics, including Ran-

domised Local Search with neighbourhood size 1 (i.e., RLS_1) (with expected runtime $0.5n^2$ [8, 6]) and the standard (1+1) Evolutionary Algorithm ((1+1) EA) (with expected runtime $(1 - o(1)) \cdot (e - 1)/2 \cdot n^2 \approx (1 - o(1))0.85914n^2$ [6]). By implementing a fitness-dependent mutation rate, the expected runtime of the (1+1) EA decreases to $\approx (1 \pm o(1))0.68n^2$ [6]. The best expected runtime achievable by unbiased (1+1) black box algorithms is $\approx (1 \pm o(1))0.388n^2$ [19, 12], which is matched by the Generalised Random Gradient (GRG) selection HH selecting from a sufficiently large constant $k = \mathcal{O}(1)$ number of low level heuristics [29]. In this paper we aim to improve greedy HHs such that they also achieve optimal performance for the standard benchmark function.

Note that other heuristic classes with higher arity operators, including Estimation of Distribution Algorithms and Convex Search Algorithms, can achieve $o(n^2)$ expected runtimes [1, 20, 33, 15].

3 The Generalised Greedy HH Does Not Have Optimal Performance

In this section, we analyse the Generalised Greedy (GG) HH, which extends the amount of time the greedily chosen heuristic is applied for, equipped with a minimal low-level heuristic set $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$. We will show that the inclusion of the exploitation period (i.e., setting $\tau > 0$) is provably beneficial to the performance of GG. However, it does not suffice to allow the HH to achieve optimal performance for the LEADINGONES (LO) function.

The following is the main result of this section, which provides an upper bound on the expected runtime of GG for LEADINGONES, for well chosen τ values. A similar result without proof was provided by Lissovoi et al. [28] for a non-optimal *linear* learning period τ and the set $H = \{1\text{BITFLIP}, 2\text{BITFLIP}\}$. Here we show that a set of *super-linear* learning periods lead to the best possible expected runtime and prove that the bound is tight up to the leading constant at the end of the section (i.e., the bound is the best possible for GG).

Corollary 1. *The expected runtime of the Generalised Greedy hyper-heuristic with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ for LEADINGONES, with $\tau \in \omega(n) \cap o(n^2)$, is at most $(1 + o(1)) \cdot (\ln(5)/8 + \arctan(2)/4)n^2 \approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.47797n^2$.*

Corollary 1 proves that GG outperforms the simple Greedy HH and RLS (i.e., its low-level heuristic) which have respectively expected runtimes of $(1 + o(1)) \cdot ((\ln 3)/2)n^2 \approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.54931n^2$ and $0.5n^2$. However, it is slower than the GRG HH with static and adaptive values for the learning period [29, 17], i.e., it does not achieve the optimal runtime achievable with the heuristic set $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$, i.e., $\approx (1 + o(1))0.423n^2$.

Before showing the prerequisite results required to reach this statement, we first prove that if the length of the exploitation phase τ is set to be too large, the performance of GG worsens.

We know that the expected time for RLS_1 to solve LO is $0.5n^2$ [12], and the expected time for RLS_2 to solve LO is infinite, since there is a non-zero chance

of sampling a solution with fitness $n - 1$ (and from here, RLS_2 cannot make progress). Clearly, for $\tau = \omega(n^2)$, there is a constant probability of selecting RLS_2 at the first decision stage, giving a runtime of $\omega(n^2)$ in expectation. We therefore consider the setting $\tau = \alpha n^2$ for some constant $\alpha > 0$.

Theorem 1. *Let $T(i)$ denote the expected runtime of the Generalised Greedy hyper-heuristic with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ for LEADINGONES with $\tau = \alpha n^2$ for some constant $\alpha > 0$ starting from a greedy decision stage at the state $\text{LO}(x) = i$. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned} T(i) &= \frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \left(\min \left\{ \alpha n^2, \frac{n(n-i)}{2} \right\} + T(\min(i+2\alpha n, n)) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{2(n-i-1)}{3n-2i-3} \cdot (\alpha n^2 + T(n - (n-1)e^{-4\alpha})) + o(n^2), \end{aligned}$$

and an upper bound on the expected runtime is given by $T(0)$.

Theorem 1 holds for any value of $\tau = \alpha n^2$ for constant $\alpha > 0$, and presents the expected runtime based on the progress of a single ‘Decision plus Exploitation’ (D+E) stage as a recursive function call. Specifically, since $\tau = \alpha n^2$, the expected progress in the LEADINGONES value in a single D+E stage is linear (unless the optimum is found in that given stage). While a closed form expression is hard to present, since the expected progress in a stage is linear, only $\mathcal{O}(1)$ recursive calls are necessary to present a runtime bound for $T(0)$.

Firstly, we note that as $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ (from above), then the bound matches exactly that as presented in Corollary 1 (i.e., $\approx 0.478n^2$). As α increases, then we expect fewer decision stages to occur; for large α , either RLS_1 is chosen in the first decision stage (and finds the optimum), or RLS_2 is chosen and finds the state $i = n - 1$. From here, RLS_2 cannot be chosen again, and thus RLS_1 will find the optimum in one step. That is, the runtime tends towards $(2/3 \cdot \alpha + 1/3 \cdot 0.5)n^2$ as α increases, and towards $0.478n^2$ as α decreases.

Now we concentrate on deriving an upper bound on the expected runtime for smaller τ (i.e., $\tau = o(n^2)$) which will allow us to derive the main result. For this we require a different proof strategy. We begin by stating a lemma on the expected time and progress for a combined Decision and Exploitation stage (i.e., the expected time and progress when making a greedy choice of low-level heuristic and applying it for τ iterations).

Lemma 1. *Let $\text{LO}(x^{(t)}) = i < n - 1$, and let $Y^{(t)} = n - i$ be the distance of the Generalised Greedy hyper-heuristic’s current solution to the LEADINGONES optimum at the start of the t^{th} Decision Stage with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ and let $\tau = o(n^2)$. Then,*

$$\begin{aligned} &E(Y^{(t)} - Y^{(t+1)} \mid Y^{(t)} \geq 2) \\ &= 2 + \frac{2 \cdot \tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n - 2i)} \pm o(1), \end{aligned}$$

and, in expectation, the next Decision Stage begins after

$$\frac{2n^2}{3n-2i} + \tau + o(n)$$

fitness evaluations if the optimum has not been reached.

As the number of iterations spent in the Decision Stage is not deterministic and not identically distributed over the optimisation process, we cannot directly apply the Variable Drift Theorem [23] to bound the expected runtime for GG. However, we can bound the expected runtime through an application of Wald's equation [37, 16]. By splitting the analysis into w phases, we can bound the expected time for a Decision and Exploitation Stage within each phase from above and use the Variable Drift Theorem to bound the expected number of Decision and Exploitation Stages required to optimise each segment. Finally, we can combine the two results to bound the total expected runtime.

Theorem 2. *The expected runtime of the Generalised Greedy hyper-heuristic with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ for LEADINGONES with $\tau = o(n^2)$ is at most $o(n^2)$, plus*

$$\sum_{j=1}^w \left(\left(\frac{2w}{3w-2j} + \frac{\tau}{n} \right) n \cdot \int_{\frac{(j-1)n}{w}}^{\frac{jn}{w}} \frac{1}{\frac{2\tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i)} + 2} di \right),$$

where $w = o(\min\{n, n^2/\tau\})$.

The proof technique for Theorem 2 partitions the search space into w phases, each representing an equal range of fitness values. The expected runtime of the GG algorithm does not depend on w . However, w does affect the upper bound on the runtime we obtain. The greater the number of phases, the tighter the upper bound the theorem statement provides, so long as $w = o(\min\{n, n^2/\tau\})$.

The upper bound in Theorem 2 holds for any sub-quadratic value of τ . This indicates that GG is not very sensitive to the parameter τ for LEADINGONES. As a result, the parameter should be easy to set in practice, as confirmed by experiments in Section 7. The best achievable expected runtime (i.e., $\approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.47797n^2$) is obtained for $\tau \in \omega(n) \cap o(n^2)$, as highlighted in Corollary 1. Theorem 3 will prove that the resulting bound is tight.

Before that, the following corollary shows that Theorem 2 provides tight bounds on GG even when $\tau = 0$ (i.e., it provides the well known expected runtime for the simple Greedy HH [29]).

Corollary 2. *The expected runtime of the simple Greedy hyper-heuristic for LEADINGONES is at most $(1 + o(1)) \cdot \frac{\ln 3}{2} n^2 \approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.54931n^2$.*

We now show that the bound from Corollary 1 is the best possible for any Greedy or Generalised HH (i.e., $\tau \in \omega(n) \cap o(n^2)$ provide the best possible runtime). To show this we analyse an *ideal* Greedy algorithm which will provide a theoretical lower bound on the expected runtime of GG. This ideal algorithm

is sped-up by getting the result of the Decision Stages ‘for free’ in every iteration and uses this result to decide which operator to apply. In particular, if the algorithm is at $\text{LO}(x) = i$, the RLS_1 operator is chosen with probability $P(\text{RLS}_1) = (n-1)/(3n-2i-3)$ and the RLS_2 operator is chosen with probability $P(\text{RLS}_2) = (2n-2i-2)/(3n-2i-3)$. This gives the same probabilities as GG, yet saves time on any Decision Stages. This algorithm is equivalent to running the Exploitation Stages of GG without the Decision Stages. Hence, its expected runtime provides a lower bound on the expected runtime of GG.

Theorem 3. *The expected runtime of the ideal greedy algorithm which, in each iteration (independently at random), applies RLS_1 with probability $(n-1)/(3n-2i-3)$ and RLS_2 with probability $(2n-2i-2)/(3n-2i-3)$, where $\text{LO}(x) = i$ is the fitness of the current solution, for LEADINGONES is $(1+o(1)) \cdot (\ln(5)/8 + \arctan(2/4)n^2 \approx (1+o(1)) \cdot 0.47797n^2$.*

This lower bound matches the upper bound of Corollary 1. Since this *ideal* Greedy algorithm is faster than GG (by design), the upper bound provided in Corollary 1 is tight.

We conclude that while GG outperforms its component low level heuristics, it is not optimal. Indeed, the optimal performance for a unary unbiased algorithm with access to the heuristic set $H_2 := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ is $\approx 0.423n^2$ which is matched by GRG with static and adaptive learning periods [17, 29].

4 Increasing the Size of the Heuristic Set Degrades Performance

We now consider the GG HH with access to the heuristic set $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_k\}$ of arbitrary size $k \in \mathcal{O}(1)$. While we know that for $k = 2$, GG is able to outperform its constituent heuristic RLS_1 , we aim to show that increasing k beyond this leads to degraded performance compared to $k = 2$.

The following lemma provides insights into the probability of finding an improvement when using the RLS_m heuristic (for $m \in \mathcal{O}(1)$).

Lemma 2 ([19, 13]). *The probability of improvement from an operator which flips m distinct bits in a bit-string (RLS_m) on the LO benchmark function, at the state $\text{LO}(x) = i$, is*

$$P[\text{Imp}_m \mid \text{LO}(x) = i] = m \cdot \frac{1}{n} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{m-1} \frac{n-i-j}{n-j}.$$

We consider again the *ideal* greedy algorithm introduced in the previous section, which gives a lower bound on the runtime of the GG algorithm.

The following theorem derives the expected running time of the ideal Greedy algorithm with access to the heuristic set $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_k\}$.

Theorem 4. *The expected runtime of the ideal greedy algorithm with access to the heuristic set $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_k\}$ is*

$$\frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{\sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)}{\sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)^2} \right) + o(n^2),$$

where $P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)$ is the probability of improvement of RLS_m at the state $\text{LO}(x) = i$.

A closed-form expression for the statement given by Theorem 4 is hard to present, but we can see that as the size of the heuristic set k increases, the expected runtime of the ideal Greedy algorithm increases. We have seen that for $k = 2$, the expected runtime is $\approx 0.478n^2$. For $k = 3$, the result given by Theorem 4 is $\approx 0.481n^2$; for $k = 4$, it is $\approx 0.487n^2$, and for $k = 5$, the expected runtime is $\approx 0.493n^2$. Since the performance of the ideal Greedy algorithm degrades as the size of the heuristic set increases, and the performance of the ideal algorithm gives a lower bound on the expected performance of the GG algorithm, we can state that the best-case performance of GG also degrades as the heuristic set size increases.

5 A Fast Greedy Selection Hyper-heuristic

In this section we analyse the proposed Fast Greedy (FG) HH which combines the decision stage of the GG HH and the exploitation stage of GRG.

The main result of this section is the following theorem, which proves that FG has optimal expected runtime for LEADINGONES when $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$. In the next section we will show that the result generalises to an arbitrary number of low-level heuristics. In Section 7, we will see experimentally that FG even outperforms the Generalised Random Gradient HH (GRG) for realistic problem sizes.

Corollary 3. *The expected runtime of the Fast Greedy hyper-heuristic with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ for LEADINGONES, with τ that satisfies both $\tau = \omega(n)$ and $\tau \leq (1/2 - \varepsilon)n \ln(n)$ for some constant $\varepsilon > 0$, is at most $(1 + o(1)) \cdot ((1 + \ln 2)/4)n^2 \approx (1 + o(1)) \cdot 0.42329n^2$.*

The following general theorem bounds the expected runtime of FG for any value of τ smaller than $1/2 \cdot n \ln n$. First, we see that FG can lead to improved performance for LEADINGONES compared to GRG; for each value of τ the upper bound achieved by FG is lower than the upper bound achieved by GRG. Secondly, the theorem allows us to identify values of τ for which the expected runtime of FG for the function is optimal; this result is highlighted in Corollary 3.

Again, we note that the proof technique for Theorem 5 partitions the search space into w phases, each representing an equal range of fitness values. The expected runtime of the FG algorithm does not depend on w . However, w does affect the upper bound on the runtime we obtain. The greater the number of phases, the tighter the upper bound the theorem statement provides, so long as $w = o(n/\exp(\tau/n))$.

Table 1. The upper bounds in the leading constants for the expected runtimes of the Generalised Greedy (Theorem 2), Fast Greedy (Theorem 5) and Generalised Random Gradient [29] hyper-heuristics for LEADINGONES with $w = 100,000$. The optimal runtime in this setting is $0.42329n^2$ to 5 s.f.

	GG	FG	GRG
$\tau = 5n$	0.49058	0.45219	0.46493
$\tau = 50n$	0.47953	0.42344	0.42363
$\tau = 1/10 \cdot n \ln n$	0.47797	0.42329	0.42329

Theorem 5. *The expected runtime of the Fast Greedy hyper-heuristic with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \text{RLS}_2\}$ for LEADINGONES, with $\tau \leq (1/2 - \varepsilon)n \ln(n)$ for some constant $\varepsilon > 0$, is at most*

$$E(T) \leq \frac{(1 + o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \left(\frac{2w + \frac{\tau}{n} \cdot (3w - 2j) + w \cdot e^{\tau/n} \cdot M_1(1) + 2(w - j + 1) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot (w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w - j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)})} \right)$$

where $w \in \omega(\max\{1, \tau/n\}) \cap o(n/\exp(\tau/n))$, $M_1(x) = \min\{\tau/n, x\}$ and

$$M_2(j, w) := \begin{cases} \frac{\tau}{n} & \text{if } j = w \text{ or } (2 - 2\frac{j}{w})^{-1} > \frac{\tau}{n} \\ (2 - 2\frac{j}{w})^{-1} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

As before, the best way to interpret the result of Theorem 5 is to consider specific values for τ . We have seen from Corollary 3 that for $\tau = \omega(n)$, FG gives the best expected runtime achievable for LEADINGONES with the low-level heuristics available, up to lower order terms. Table 1 gives the theoretical upper bounds achieved by GG and FG for LEADINGONES for some interesting values of τ . Also included within Table 1 are the values obtained by the theoretical results in [29] for Generalised Random Gradient.

6 Runtime of FG with Larger Heuristic Sizes

In this section we show that the FG HH can achieve optimal performance for LEADINGONES when equipped with $k = \mathcal{O}(1)$ low level heuristics, thus that its expected runtime matches the best expected runtime achievable provided by Theorem 12 in [29]. Compared to Theorem 5 we only consider the optimal range of parameter τ values, which simplifies the proof.

Theorem 6. *The expected runtime of the Fast Greedy hyper-heuristic with $H := \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_k\}$ for LEADINGONES, with $\tau = \omega(n)$ and $\tau \leq (1/k - \varepsilon)n \ln(n)$ for some constant $\varepsilon > 0$, is at most*

$$E(T_{k, \text{Opt}}) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i=0}^{\frac{n}{k}-1} \frac{1}{\frac{k}{n} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{n-i-j}{n-j}} + \sum_{m=1}^{k-1} \sum_{i=\frac{n}{m+1}}^{\frac{n}{m}-1} \frac{1}{\frac{m}{n} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{m-1} \frac{n-i-j}{n-j}} \right) \pm o(n^2).$$

Fig. 1. Average number of fitness function evaluations required by the hyper-heuristics with $k = 2$ operators to find the LEADINGONES optimum for $n = 10,000$ (solid), $n = 50,000$ (dashed).

Theorem 6 shows that FG can achieve the same optimal asymptotic runtime for LEADINGONES as GRG using the same parameter settings for τ , and that its performance improves as the size of the heuristic set increases (up to an arbitrary $\mathcal{O}(1)$ operators). We further expect that FG is faster than GRG in practice, since it is able to make a more informed choice of which heuristic to apply in the gradient-descent style exploitation phase. While this comes at the cost of the decision stage, we believe the tradeoff favours FG. In Section 7.2 we show experimentally that FG is able to outperform GRG for various parameter settings of τ for different heuristic set sizes, implying it is faster in practice for realistic problem sizes.

7 Experimental Results

In the previous sections we proved the performance of the considered HHs for the LEADINGONES benchmark function for large enough problem sizes n . In this section we present some experimental results to shed light on their performance for problem sizes up to $n = 10^5$. All parameter combinations have been simulated 10,000 times.

7.1 Two Low-level Heuristics ($k = 2$)

We first consider GG and FG using two operators only (i.e., $H = \{RLS_1, RLS_2\}$) and look at the impact of the exploitation period τ and problem size n .

Figure 1 shows the average runtimes for the two generalised HHs, as well as Generalised Random Gradient [29] for comparison, for LEADINGONES for $n = 10,000$ and $n = 50,000$, illustrating the effect τ has on the runtime. For GG, we see that for the larger problem size, the relative runtimes improve slightly. The figure implies that for a sufficiently large τ , GG outperforms RLS; in particular,

Fig. 2. Average number of fitness function evaluations required by the (a) Generalised Greedy hyper-heuristic and (b) Fast Greedy hyper-heuristic to find the LEADINGONES optimum, $n = 100,000$.

for every value of τ greater than approximately $0.3n \ln n$ (for $n = 50,000$ this value is 162,297). Also, for every $\tau \geq n \ln n$ the average runtime of GG does not change much, confirming the robustness of the HH to the choice of τ , indicated by Corollary 1. FG showcases a similar reliance on the parameter τ as Generalised Random Gradient. FG, however, does have improved performance over GRG for both problem sizes, confirming that incorporating the Decision Stage of GG within the HH framework has a positive effect on the runtime.

7.2 More Than Two Low-level Heuristics ($k \geq 2$)

We now consider the generalised HHs using k operators (i.e., $H_k := \{\text{RLS}_1, \dots, \text{RLS}_k\}$) and look at the impact of the exploitation period τ and heuristic set size k .

Figure 2 (left) shows the average runtimes for GG when choosing from heuristic sets of RLS operators with neighbourhood sizes 2 to 5 for LEADINGONES for a problem size of $n = 100,000$ and a large range of τ values. Unlike GRG, which exploits a high-performing operator while running for a shorter time with low-performing operators, GG runs each chosen operator for a fixed period of time. Involving more operators means a lower chance of choosing the best operator in the Decision Stage and hence, GG displays a detrimental performance when more operators are included. We see that GG using the heuristic set H_2 remains the best performing HH throughout, confirming our theoretical results. Although the performance of the GG using the set H_5 is the worst, it is worth noting that even this algorithm outperforms the single operator algorithm RLS (i.e., $0.5n^2$). For this HH, the detriment in performance between $\tau = 50n$ and $\tau = 750n$ is $\approx 0.01n^2$, confirming that GG is very robust to the choice of τ .

Figure 2 (right) shows the runtime for FG for LEADINGONES for $n = 100,000$. While the HH displays similar trends to GRG, we note that the best average runtime for each heuristic set H_k is smaller than the respective average runtime

for GRG with the same heuristic set. This implies that, while the Decision Stage can be detrimental in the case of GG including more operators, the Exploitation Stage idea can correct for poor operator choices or expensive Decision Stages, leading to faster average runtimes. For example, the best average runtime of FG using the heuristic set H_5 with $\tau \approx 0.62n \ln(n)$ is $\approx 0.418n^2$, smaller than the best-possible expected runtime when using the heuristic set H_2 shown in Corollary 3, of $\approx 0.423n^2$.

8 Conclusion

Previous work has shown that the simple Greedy hyper-heuristic has general poor performance by not exploiting the greedily chosen heuristic for a sufficient amount of time [28]. Thus a Generalised Greedy (GG) HH was proposed by the authors that allows for the application of the chosen heuristic for an exploitation period τ . The authors showed promising results for the GG HH equipped with two operators as it was proven to outperform its low level heuristics for the LEADINGONES benchmark using a linear exploitation period.

In this paper we proved that the best possible runtime achievable by the GG HH with two operators for LO is obtained for super-linear exploitation periods and is suboptimal. Furthermore, we show that its performance degrades as the size of the available heuristic set increases. To aid the design of efficient Greedy HH, we proposed a Fast Greedy (FG) HH, which incorporates the advantages of the decision stage of greedy HHs with those of the exploitation stage of random gradient HHs. We have rigorously proved that FG has optimal expected performance for LEADINGONES with low-level heuristic sets of arbitrary size, while we have shown experimentally that compared to the Generalised Random Gradient (GRG HH) it is faster in practice, and is able to outperform it for shorter values of the learning period τ .

Several directions should be naturally explored in future work. Firstly, the HH's performance on a broader class of problems, including classical ones from combinatorial optimisation, should be analysed. In particular, problems where FG outperforms GRG and vice-versa should be identified, thus aiding the choice of the HH for the problem at hand. Secondly, FG should be generalised further by allowing it to automatically learn how to adapt τ , as already shown to be effective for the Random Gradient HH [17], or by selecting heuristics proportionally (rather than in an elitist way) based on their performance in the decision stage [24]. Finally, the performance of both FG and GRG should be compared to that of more sophisticated HHs that are more commonly applied in practical applications, such as the choice function (reinforcement learning) approach [9] which keeps track of the historical performance of each low-level heuristic and uses this information to decide which one to be applied next.

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APPENDIX

We define $[n] := \{1, \dots, n\}$.

8.1 Mathematical Techniques

We will use the following mathematical techniques for the analyses of the HHs throughout the paper.

We begin with two theorems that bound the expected runtime of stochastic algorithms when the drift (expected fitness change in one iteration) can be bounded respectively by a constant and a function of the state of the optimisation process.

Theorem 7. Additive Drift Theorem [22] *Let $\{X_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ be a Markov process over a finite set of states S , and $g : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_0^+$ a function that assigns a non-negative real number to every state. Let the time to reach the optimum be $T := \min\{t \geq 0 \mid g(X_t) = 0\}$. If there exists $\delta > 0$ such that at any time step $t \geq 0$ and at any state $X_t \geq 0$ the following condition holds:*

$$E(g(X_t) - g(X_{t+1}) \mid g(X_t) > 0) \geq \delta,$$

then

$$E(T \mid X_0) \leq \frac{g(X_0)}{\delta} \quad \text{and} \quad E(T) \leq \frac{E(g(X_0))}{\delta}.$$

Theorem 8. Variable Drift Theorem [23] *Let $(X_t)_{t \geq 0}$ be a stochastic process over some state space $S \subseteq \{0\} \cup [x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$, where $x_{\min} > 0$. Let $h(x)$ be an integrable, monotone increasing function on $[x_{\min}, x_{\max}]$ such that $E(X_t - X_{t+1} \mid X_t \geq x_{\min}) \geq h(X_t)$. Then it holds for the first hitting time $T := \min\{t \mid X_t = 0\}$ that*

$$E(T \mid X_0) \leq \frac{x_{\min}}{h(x_{\min})} + \int_{x_{\min}}^{X_0} \frac{1}{h(x)} dx.$$

The following is useful for bounding stochastic sums of stochastic variables.

Theorem 9. Wald's Equation [37, 16] *Let T be a random variable with bounded expectation and let X_1, X_2, \dots be non-negative random variables with $E(X_i \mid T \geq i) \leq C$. Then*

$$E\left(\sum_{i=1}^T X_i\right) \leq E(T) \cdot C.$$

The following theorem gives the expected runtime of any unbiased (1+1) black box algorithms for LEADINGONES.

Theorem 10 ([6, 12]). *The expected time needed for a (1+1) algorithm to find the optimum of LEADINGONES given random initialisation is*

$$\frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} A_i,$$

where A_i is the expected time needed to find an improvement given a solution x with fitness $\text{LO}(x) = i$.

8.2 Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. In a given exploitation stage, suppose RLS_1 is chosen at the state $\text{LO}(x) = i$. Then, it either runs for $\tau = \alpha n^2$ steps, or finds the optimum in $(n - i) \cdot n/2$ steps, i.e., it runs for $\min\{\alpha n^2, n(n - i)/2\}$ iterations. RLS_1 produces a success in each iteration with probability $1/n$. Thus, in expectation, there are αn successes (if the optimum is not found), contributing to an expected fitness increase of $\min\{2\alpha n, (n - i)\}$ (see e.g., Theorem 10). Thus, given an initial state i , GG would end up in state $i' = \min\{i + 2\alpha n, n\}$ after $\min\{\alpha n^2, n(n - i)/2\}$ iterations.

Since there is a finite chance that RLS_2 reaches the state $\text{LO}(x) = n - 1$ (from which it cannot find an improvement), we thus assume it can never reach the optimum. Suppose RLS_2 is chosen and applied for αn^2 steps from the state $\text{LO}(x) = i$. Thus, it reaches a state $i' = i + k$, where k satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha n^2 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=i}^{i+k} \frac{n(n-1)}{2(n-j-1)} = (1 \pm o(1)) \cdot \frac{n^2}{4} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{n-i-1}{n-i-k-1} \right); \\ \implies k &= (1 \pm o(1))(1 - e^{-4\alpha}) \cdot (n - i - 1). \end{aligned}$$

That is, it reaches the state $i' = n - (1 \pm o(1))(n - i - 1)e^{-4\alpha}$.

The probability of each heuristic being selected in the Decision Stage at state $\text{LO}(x) = i$ (given by the *first hit probability* $P(\text{RLS}_k)$ for $k \in \{1, 2\}$) is

$$P(\text{RLS}_1) = \frac{1/n}{1/n + 2(n-i-1)/(n(n-1))} = \frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3},$$

for RLS_1 and

$$P(\text{RLS}_2) = \frac{2(n-i-1)/(n(n-1))}{1/n + 2(n-i-1)/(n(n-1))} = \frac{2n-2i-2}{3n-2i-3},$$

for RLS_2 . From Lemma 1, we know decision stages will take $o(n^2)$ time, so any time spent in exploitation stages will asymptotically dominate (when $\tau = \Omega(n^2)$).

Thus, we can define the expected runtime by a recursive process $T(i)$, dependent on state i , assuming a new Decision Stage begins at this state.

$$T(i) = \frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \left(\min \left\{ \alpha n^2, \frac{n(n-i)}{2} \right\} + T(\min(i+2\alpha n, n)) \right) \\ + \frac{2(n-i-1)}{3n-2i-3} \cdot (\alpha n^2 + T(n - (n-1)e^{-4\alpha})) + o(n^2).$$

For an upper bound on the total expected runtime, we can pessimistically assume a starting state of $\text{LO}(x) = 0$. \square

Proof of Lemma 1. We look at the expected number of fitness evaluations used in the Decision and Exploitation (D+E) Stage, given the starting position $\text{LO}(x) = i$.

During the Decision Stage, GG will run both heuristics until one of them is successful (i.e., makes an improvement in the fitness). The expected number of fitness evaluations for this to happen, noting that evaluations performed in parallel contribute separately to the final runtime, is given by:

$$E(T_{\text{DS}_i}) = 2 \cdot \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \right) \left(1 - \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)} \right) \right)^{-1} \\ = \frac{2n^2}{3n-2i-2} = \frac{2n^2}{3n-2i} + o(n).$$

The probability of each heuristic being selected in the Decision Stage (given by the *first hit probability* $P(\text{RLS}_k)$ for $k \in \{1, 2\}$) is

$$P(\text{RLS}_1) = \frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3}; \quad P(\text{RLS}_2) = \frac{2n-2i-2}{3n-2i-3},$$

as with the proof of Theorem 1.

In the Exploitation Stage, the operator which was selected in the Decision Stage is applied for τ steps. Throughout the two stages, the function value will increase. We can bound the total expected fitness increase from above by keeping $\text{LO}(x) = i$ constant throughout (i.e., using the value from the Decision Stage) and bound it from below by applying a high-probability bound on the number of observed LEADINGONES improvements. The highest probability of a fitness improvement occurs when using the RLS_2 operator at $i = 0$; i.e. $\frac{2}{n}$. Since $\tau = o(n^2)$, we can use Chernoff bounds [11] to bound the number of successes in τ steps as $o(n)$ with probability $1 - 2^{-\Omega(n)}$ (i.e., the probability of $\Omega(n)$ successes in τ steps is at most $2^{-\Omega(n)}$). Hence, we can bound the number of LEADINGONES improvements from above by considering $\text{LO}(x) = i + o(n)$. The probability of each operator being selected will remain the same, since this is based on the original value of i at the Decision Stage.

Hence, the expected progress of the Exploitation Stage in τ iterations is at most

$$\begin{aligned} & 2 \cdot \tau \cdot \left(\frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \frac{1}{n} + \frac{2n-2i-2}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \frac{2(n-i-1)}{n(n-1)} \right) \\ &= \frac{2\tau(5n^2 - (8i+10)n + 4i^2 - 8i - 5)}{n(n-1)(3n-2i-3)} = \frac{2\tau(5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i)} + o(1). \end{aligned}$$

and at least

$$\begin{aligned} & 2 \cdot \tau \cdot \left(\frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \frac{1}{n} + \frac{2n-2i-2}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \frac{2(n-(i+o(n))-1)}{n(n-1)} \right) \\ &= \frac{2\tau(5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i)} \pm o(1). \end{aligned}$$

We further note that for $\text{LO}(x) = n-1$, the Decision Stage takes an expected $2n$ iterations and will conclude the optimisation process.

Summing the expected progress and expected number of fitness evaluations performed in both stages (i.e., τ iterations in the Exploitation Stage) yields the Lemma statement. \square

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $\text{LO}(x) = i$ denote the current state. We divide the analysis into w phases of length n/w . During phase $j \in [w]$, the LEADINGONES value of the current solution is at least $(j-1)n/w$ and less than jn/w . We can bound the expected time for a D+E Stage (using Lemma 1) in the j^{th} phase (where $(j-1)n/w \leq i \leq jn/w - 1$) by

$$\frac{2n^2}{3n-2i} + o(n) + \tau \leq \left(\frac{2w}{3w-2j} + \frac{\tau}{n} \right) \cdot n + o(n).$$

Within each phase, we will use the Variable Drift Theorem (Theorem 8) to bound the number of expected D+E Stages that occur by looking at the expected LEADINGONES progress that happens in a D+E Stage, i.e., in expectation at most $(2w/(3w-2j) + \tau/n) \cdot n + o(n)$ steps. We note that there may be some minor overlap between phases (i.e., if the LEADINGONES value increases into the next phase), although this will result in the addition of at most $\tau \cdot w = o(n^2)$ iterations throughout the process.

To apply the Variable Drift Theorem, let

$$h(x) = E(Y^{(t)} - Y^{(t+1)} \mid Y^{(t)}) = \frac{2 \cdot \tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i)} + 2 - o(1),$$

using Lemma 1. We consider $Y^{(t)} = 0$ to be the end of the phase. Let $x_{\min} = 1$ represent the point $jn/w - 1$ and we note that $x_{\min}/h(x_{\min}) = \mathcal{O}(n/\tau)$. Hence,

by the Variable Drift Theorem, the expected runtime while GG is in the j^{th} phase is

$$\begin{aligned} E(T_j) &\leq o(n) + \frac{x_{\min}}{h(x_{\min})} \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{2w}{3w-2j} + \frac{\tau}{n} \right) n \cdot \int_{\frac{(j-1)n}{w}}^{\frac{jn}{w}-1} \left(\frac{1}{\frac{2\tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i)} + 2} + o(1) \right) di \\ &\leq \left(\frac{2w}{3w-2j} + \frac{\tau}{n} \right) n \int_{\frac{(j-1)n}{w}}^{\frac{jn}{w}} \frac{1}{\frac{2\tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i-2)} + 2} di + \mathcal{O}(\max\{\tau, n\}). \end{aligned}$$

The total expected runtime, given by an application of Wald's equation (Theorem 9) will be at most equal to the sum of the expected runtimes of each phase, plus some lower-order terms amounting to at most $\mathcal{O}(\max\{\tau, n\}) \cdot w = o(n^2)$. Thus,

$$E(T) \leq \left(\sum_{j=1}^w E(T_j) \right) + o(n^2).$$

□

Proof of Corollary 2. To prove the corollary, we insert the value $\tau = 0$ into the result for Theorem 2.

$$\begin{aligned} E(T) &\leq \sum_{k=1}^w \frac{2w}{3w-2j} \cdot n \cdot \int_{\frac{(j-1)n}{w}}^{\frac{jn}{w}} \frac{1}{2} di \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^w \frac{2w}{3w-2j} \cdot n \cdot \frac{n}{2w} = n^2 \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \frac{1}{3w-2j} = (1 + o(1)) \cdot \frac{\ln 3}{2} \cdot n^2. \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Proof of Corollary 1. Since $\tau = \omega(n)$, we have $\frac{2w}{3w-2j} + \frac{\tau}{n} = (1 + o(1)) \cdot \frac{\tau}{n}$ and

$$\frac{2\tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n - 2i)} + 2 = (1 + o(1)) \cdot \frac{2\tau(5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n - 2i)}.$$

We can thus simplify the expected runtime of the HH given in Theorem 2:

$$\begin{aligned} E(T) &\leq \sum_{j=1}^w \left(\left(\frac{2w}{3w-2j} + \frac{\tau}{n} \right) n \cdot \int_{\frac{(j-1)n}{w}}^{\frac{jn}{w}} \frac{1}{\frac{2\tau \cdot (5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2)}{n^2(3n-2i)} + 2} di \right) + o(n^2) \\ &= \frac{n^2}{2} \sum_{j=1}^w \left(\int_{\frac{(j-1)n}{w}}^{\frac{jn}{w}} \frac{3n-2i}{5n^2 - 8in + 4i^2} di \right) + o(n^2) \\ &\leq \frac{n^2}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4} \ln 5 + \frac{1}{2} \arctan 2 \right) + o(n^2) = (1 + o(1)) \cdot \left(\frac{\ln 5}{8} + \frac{\arctan 2}{4} \right) n^2, \end{aligned}$$

given the same bounds on w as Theorem 2. □

Proof of Theorem 3. We use Theorem 10 and the law of total expectation to give the result (since the ideal Greedy algorithm fits into the (1+1) framework).

$$\begin{aligned}
E(T) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{n-1}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \frac{1}{n} + \frac{2n-2i-2}{3n-2i-3} \cdot \frac{2n-2i-2}{n(n-1)} \right)^{-1} \\
&= \frac{n(n-1)}{2} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{3n-2i-3}{(2n-2i-2)^2 + (n-1)^2} \\
&= (1+o(1)) \cdot \left(\frac{\ln 5}{8} + \frac{\arctan 2}{4} \right) n^2. \quad \square
\end{aligned}$$

Proof of Theorem 4. Recall that the ideal greedy algorithm gets the result of the Decision Stage for free. For RLS_m (where $m \in [k]$), the probability that it is chosen by during the greedy decision phase when $\text{LO}(x) = i$ is given by

$$P(\text{RLS}_m \mid i) = \frac{P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)}{\sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{Imp}_j \mid i)}.$$

If RLS_m is chosen, it is successful with probability $P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)$ and thus the expected progress in one iteration at $\text{LO}(x) = i$ (denoted by A_k^i) is

$$A_k^i = \left(\sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{RLS}_m \mid i) \cdot P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i) \right)^{-1} = \frac{\sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)}{\sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{Imp}_m \mid i)^2}.$$

The final runtime is then given by an application of Theorem 10. □

Proof Of Theorem 5. This proof follows a similar structure to the proof of Theorem 8 in [29]. That is, we partition the optimisation process into w phases based on the value of the LEADINGONES fitness function: during phase j , the LEADINGONES value of the current solution is at least $(j-1) \cdot n/w$ and less than $j \cdot n/w$.

We bound the final expected runtime from above by the sum of the values of T_j , the expected runtime of each phase of the process, plus the expected times taken to reach the first operator decision within each phase. Since the analysis of $E(T_j)$ requires an operator choice, we bound the expected runtime $E(T) \leq \sum_{j=1}^w (E(T_j) + E(S_{j+1}))$, where S_{j+1} is a random variable denoting the expected number of fitness evaluations between the first solution in phase $j+1$ being constructed and the first Decision Stage of phase j beginning. We note that with the same parameter combinations as those used for the proof for GRG in [29] (i.e., $\tau \leq (1/2 - \varepsilon) n \ln(n)$ for some constant $\varepsilon > 0$, and $w = o(n/\exp(\tau/n))$), the contribution of the S_{j+1} terms can be bounded by $o(n^2)$.

We let N_j denote the number of Decision Stages within phase j , and let $E(X_j)$ denote an upper bound on the number of fitness function evaluations in a ‘D+E’ stage in phase j . Then, by Wald’s equation,

$$E(T_j) \leq E(N_j)E(X_j).$$

We can bound $E(N_j)$ from above by bounding the expected number of improvements found from the ‘D+E’ Stage of the chosen operator from below and using the Additive Drift Theorem (Theorem 7) to find the expected number of operator selections required to enter the next phase.

Let F_1 and F_2 denote the events that the RLS_1 and RLS_2 operators fail to find an improvement during τ iterations. Then, $P(F_1) = (1 - 1/n)^\tau$ and thus

$$P(F_1) \leq e^{-\tau/n}.$$

For $P(F_2)$, we have that in stage j , an individual has at most $i = jn/w - 1$ and at least $i = (j - 1)n/w$ 1-bits. Thus:

$$P(F_2) \leq \left(1 - 2 \cdot \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{n - (jn/w - 1) - 1}{n - 1}\right)^\tau \leq e^{-2\tau/n(1-j/w)}.$$

Again, we opt to ignore any progress made by ‘D+E’ stages with synchronous successes, accounting for this by adding a lower-order $\mathcal{O}(\tau + n)$ term to the expected runtime.

We use the *First Hit Probability* to look at the probability of each operator being chosen (denoted $P(\text{RLS}_1)$ and $P(\text{RLS}_2)$ respectively):

$$P(\text{RLS}_1) = \frac{n - 1}{3n - 2i - 3}; \quad P(\text{RLS}_2) = \frac{2n - 2i - 2}{3n - 2i - 3}.$$

Note that in phase j , with $\frac{(j-1)n}{w} - 1 \leq i \leq \frac{jn}{w} - 1$, we can bound the two probabilities:

$$P(\text{RLS}_1) \geq \frac{w}{3w - 2j + 2}; \quad P(\text{RLS}_2) \geq \frac{2w - 2j}{3w - 2j}.$$

We look at finding a lower bound for $E(D_j)$, the expected number of improvements produced following an operator ‘D+E’ Stage in phase j . Since we are looking for a lower bound, we use the lower bound for the probability of choosing each operator and an upper bound on the probability of each operator failing to find an improvement during τ iterations. Note there is 1 improvement from the Decision Stage.

$$\begin{aligned} E(D_j) &\geq 1 + P(\text{RLS}_1) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{P(F_1)} - 1\right) + P(\text{RLS}_2) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{P(F_2)} - 1\right) \\ &\geq \frac{w}{3w - 2j + 2} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{e^{-\tau/n}} - 1\right) + \frac{2w - 2j}{3w - 2j} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{e^{-2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} - 1\right) \\ &\geq \frac{w}{3w - 2j + 2} \cdot e^{\tau/n} + \frac{2(w - j)}{3w - 2j} \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \\ &\geq \frac{w}{3w - 2j + 2} \cdot e^{\tau/n} + \frac{2(w - j)}{3w - 2j + 2} \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}. \end{aligned}$$

In each phase, in expectation, $n/(2w)$ fitness improvements are needed to exit the phase. If each random operator decision leads to at most $E(D_j)$ improvements, by the Additive Drift Theorem, the expected number of ‘D+E’ Stages required to complete phase j , $E(N_j)$ satisfies:

$$\begin{aligned} E(N_j) &\leq \frac{n/(2w)}{E(D_j)} \\ &\leq \frac{n}{2w} \cdot \frac{1}{\frac{w}{3w-2j+2} \cdot e^{\tau/n} + \frac{2(w-j)}{3w-2j+2} \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \\ &\leq \frac{n(3w-2j+2)}{2w} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

We now look at bounding $E(X_j)$, an upper bound on the number of fitness function evaluations for a ‘D+E’ Stage within phase j .

The worst case expected time for the duration of the Decision Stage in phase j is

$$E(T_{DS_j}) \leq 2 \cdot \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{n} \right) \left(1 - \frac{2(w-j)}{w(n-1)} \right) \right)^{-1} = \frac{2nw}{3w-2j}.$$

We can also bound $E(X_j \mid \text{RLS}_k)$, the expected iterations before a selected operator ($k \in \{1, 2\}$) fails to produce an improvement within τ iterations, from above:

$$\begin{aligned} E(X_j \mid \text{RLS}_1) &\leq \tau + (1/P(F_1) - 1) \cdot \min\{\tau, n\} \\ E(X_j \mid \text{RLS}_2) &\leq \tau + (1/P(F_2) - 1) \cdot \min\{\tau, n/(2-2j/w)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} E(X_j) &\leq E(T_{DS_j}) + P(\text{RLS}_1) \cdot E(X_j \mid \text{RLS}_1) + P(\text{RLS}_2) \cdot E(X_j \mid \text{RLS}_2) \\ &\leq \frac{2nw}{3w-2j} + \tau + \frac{w}{3w-2j} \cdot \frac{\min\{\tau, n\}}{e^{-\tau/n} - 1/n} \\ &\quad + \frac{2w-2j+2}{3w-2j+2} \cdot \frac{\min\{\tau, n/(2-2j/w)\}}{e^{-2\tau/n(1-(j-1)/w)} - 2/n} \\ &\leq \frac{2nw}{3w-2j} + \tau + \frac{w}{3w-2j} \cdot \frac{\min\{\tau, n\}}{e^{-\tau/n} - 1/n} \\ &\quad + \frac{2w-2j+2}{3w-2j} \cdot \frac{\min\{\tau, n/(2-2j/w)\}}{e^{-2\tau/n(1-(j-1)/w)} - 2/n}. \end{aligned}$$

If $j = w$, then $\min\{\tau/n, (2-2j/w)^{-1}\}$ is undefined. However, we know that the chosen operator would only be applied for a maximum of τ steps. We thus refer to the functions $M_1(x) = \min\{\tau/n, x\}$ and $M_2(j, w)$ from now on, where

$$M_2(j, w) := \begin{cases} \tau/n & \text{if } j = w \text{ or} \\ & (2-2j/w)^{-1} > \tau/n \\ (2-2j/w)^{-1} & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Now, $E(X_j)$ can be simplified (including the simplification in the exponent at the expense of a lower order term, since we have $w = \omega(\tau/n)$) to:

$$E(X_j) \leq \frac{(1 + o(1))n}{3w - 2j} \cdot \left(2w + \frac{\tau}{n}(3w - 2j) + we^{\tau/n}M_1(1) + (2w - 2j + 2)e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}M_2(j, w) \right).$$

Finally, we bound the overall expected runtime of the HH. We have:

$$E(T) \leq (1 + o(1)) \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w E(N_j)E(X_j),$$

and hence

$$E(T) \leq \frac{(1 + o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \left[\sum_{j=1}^w \frac{3w - 2j + 2}{3w - 2j} \left(\frac{2w + \frac{\tau}{n}(3w - 2j) + we^{\tau/n}M_1(1) + (2(w - j + 1))e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot (w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w - j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)})} \right) \right].$$

Since the theorem requires $w = \omega(1)$, we have $\frac{3w-2j+2}{3w-2j} = 1 + o(1)$ and can thus simplify the result further:

$$E(T) \leq \frac{(1 + o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \left(\frac{2w + \frac{\tau}{n}(3w - 2j) + w \cdot e^{\tau/n} \cdot M_1(1) + 2(w - j + 1) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot (w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w - j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)})} \right). \quad \square$$

Proof Of Corollary 3. Consider first the terms $M_1(1)$ and $M_2(j, w)$ in the statement of Theorem 5. Since we have $\tau = \omega(n)$, we have $\tau/n = \omega(1)$ and hence $M_1(1) = 1$. For $M_2(j, w)$, note that for the first half of the search, $M_2(j, w) = (2 - 2j/w)^{-1}$ and in the second half of the search, $M_2(j, w) = \mathcal{O}(\tau/n) = \mathcal{O}(\log n)$ for any constant $c > 0$ (there is a special case when $j = w$ in which $M_2(j, w) = \tau/n = \mathcal{O}(\log n)$). Note also that $\tau/n = \omega(1)$ and $\frac{3w-2j+2}{3w-2j} = 1 + o(1)$.

Hence, by Theorem 5, the expected runtime will become:

$$\begin{aligned}
E(T) &\leq \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \left(\frac{2w + \frac{\tau}{n} \cdot (3w - 2j) + w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + (2(w-j+1)) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot (w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)})} \right) \\
&= \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \left[\frac{1}{w} \cdot \left(\frac{2w + \frac{\tau}{n} \cdot (3w - 2j)}{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j+1) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \right] \\
&= \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \frac{1}{w} \left(\frac{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j+1) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Note that the exponential terms will dominate the summation term (since $\tau/n = \omega(1)$). When $j > w/2$, we note that $w \cdot e^{\tau/n} = \omega(2(w-j+1) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)})$ and this term will dominate the other. Vice versa for $j < w/2$. We consider $j = w/2$ as a special case:

$$\begin{aligned}
E(T) &\leq \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^w \frac{1}{w} \left(\frac{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j+1) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot M_2(j, w)}{w \cdot e^{\tau/n} + 2(w-j) \cdot e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \right) \\
&= \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^{w/2-1} \frac{1}{w} \cdot \frac{2(w-j+1)}{2(w-j)} \cdot \frac{e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)} \cdot (2-2j/w)^{-1}}{e^{2\tau/n(1-j/w)}} \right) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{w} \cdot \frac{(2w+2)e^{2\tau/n}}{2w \cdot e^{2\tau/n}} + \left(\sum_{j=w/2+1}^w \frac{1}{w} \cdot \frac{e^{\tau/n}}{e^{\tau/n}} \right) \right] \\
&= \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{2} \cdot \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^{w/2-1} \frac{1}{w} \cdot (2-2j/w)^{-1} \right) + \frac{1}{w} + \left(\sum_{j=w/2+1}^w \frac{1}{w} \right) \right] \\
&= \frac{(1+o(1))n^2}{4} \cdot \left[\left(\sum_{j=1}^{w/2} \frac{1}{w-j} \right) + 1 \right] \\
&= (1+o(1)) \cdot \left(\frac{1 + \ln 2}{4} \right) n^2.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of Theorem 6. Recall that the success probability of RLS_m at $\text{LO}(x) = i$ is

$$P(S_m | i) := \frac{m}{n} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{m-1} \frac{n-i-j}{n-j}.$$

We refer to an operator as *optimal* if it yields the highest probability of success based on the current LO value. From [29], we know that RLS_m is optimal when $\frac{n}{m+1} \leq i \leq \frac{n}{m} - 1$ (unless $m = k$, in which case RLS_k is optimal for $0 \leq i \leq \frac{n}{k} - 1$); we refer to this as the operator's *optimal period*.

In a given Decision Stage, the probability that a given operator RLS_m is selected is given by the first hit probability:

$$P(\text{RLS}_m) = \frac{P(S_m)}{\sum_{r=1}^k P(S_r)},$$

where the state i is dropped from the notation for brevity. Since the optimal operator has the highest chance of a success during its optimal period (by definition), clearly, in such a period, the value of $P(\text{RLS}_m)$ satisfies $P(\text{RLS}_m) > 1/k$ (and for $r \in [k] \setminus m$, $P(\text{RLS}_r) < P(\text{RLS}_m)$). That is, in each operator's optimal period, we are more likely to use the optimal operator compared to a random choice.

The remainder of the proof shows that the Fast Greedy (FG) HH is at least as fast as the Generalised Random Gradient (GRG) HH in expectation for LEADINGONES in the given setting, and thus the Theorem statement holds. Recall that GRG picks a low-level heuristic at random in its Decision Stage, which takes zero iterations.

Ignoring the time before the first Decision Stage of a phase and the time during the Decision Stage itself for FG, it follows that in each period, the optimal operator will be used more often for FG than for GRG. Thus, if, for FG, the time spent in Decision Stages and the time until the first Decision Stage in a period is a lower-order term, the expected time spent in each period is smaller for FG than for GRG (for the same upper bound on τ), since the optimal operator is the most efficient and is used more, and thus non-optimal operators will be used less.

Therefore, in order to prove that FG has optimal runtime for LO (as with GRG), we need to prove the following:

1. The expected time spent in Decision Stages is asymptotically smaller than the expected time spent in Exploitation Stages for FG;
2. The expected time spent in Exploitation Stages is smaller for FG than for GRG;
3. The total expected time spent between the first solution constructed in a period and the first Decision Stage in a period is $o(n^2)$.

We firstly prove the first part. We note that since the heuristic set contains RLS_1 , which has a probability of success of $1/n$, an improvement can be found in at most kn iterations in expectation, which is $\Theta(n)$ for $k = \Theta(1)$. Since we

select $\tau = \omega(n)$, we know the expected time spent in exploitation stages is $\omega(n)$, which is asymptotically larger than the time spent in Decision Stages.

We now prove the second part, by showing that the total number of D+E stages throughout the whole optimisation process is smaller for FG than for GRG. To do this, we follow the proof idea from Theorem 5, extended for k operators. Specifically, we partition the optimisation process into $w = \log^2 n$ phases based on the LO value, where phase j corresponds to $(j-1)n/w \leq \text{LO}(x) < jn/w$. Since $w = \omega(1)$, during phase j , we can bound the probability of success of RLS_m :

$$P(S_m^j) = (1 \pm o(1)) \cdot \frac{m}{n} \left(1 - \frac{j}{w}\right)^{m-1}.$$

Letting F_m denote the event that RLS_m fails to find an improvement within τ iterations, we can therefore bound $P(F_m^j)$, the probability that RLS_m fails to find an improvement within τ iterations within stage j as:

$$P(F_m^j) = (1 - P(S_m^j))^\tau = (1 \pm o(1)) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{m\tau}{n} \left(1 - \frac{j}{w}\right)^{m-1}\right).$$

We now seek a bound for $E(D_j)$, the expected number of improvements following a D+E stage during phase j . We again consider the first hit probability as the probability of each operator being selected in a decision stage in phase j (denoted $P(\text{RLS}_m^j)$):

$$P(\text{RLS}_m^j) = \frac{P(S_m^j)}{\sum_{r=1}^k P(S_r^j)} = (1 \pm o(1)) \cdot \frac{m(j-1)^2}{(w-j)(w+kj)} \left(1 - \frac{j}{w}\right)^{m-k}.$$

We can therefore bound $E(D_j)$ from below:

$$\begin{aligned} E(D_j) &\geq 1 + \sum_{m=1}^k P(\text{RLS}_m) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{P(F_m)} - 1\right) \\ &\geq \sum_{m=1}^k \left[\frac{m(j-1)^2}{(w-j)(w+kj)} \left(1 - \frac{j}{w}\right)^{m-k} \cdot \left(\exp\left(\frac{m\tau}{n} \left(1 - \frac{j}{w}\right)^{m-1}\right)\right) \right] - 1. \end{aligned}$$

In order to arrive at the statement, we note that since each improvement leads to an expected fitness increase of 2, the number of D+E stages within phase j can be bounded by

$$E(N_j) \leq n/(2w)/E(D_j).$$

Thus, we require that $E(D_j)$ is greater than the corresponding term for GRG, which is [29]:

$$\frac{1}{k} \left(\sum_{m=1}^k \exp\left(\frac{m\tau}{n} \left(1 - \frac{j}{w}\right)^{m-1}\right) \right) - 1.$$

This follows straightforwardly from the fact that more effective operators (including the optimal operator) are more likely to be chosen in the Decision Stage

of FG (i.e., with probability $> 1/k$), while less effective operators are less likely to be chosen (i.e., with probability $< 1/k$) within a given period.

For the third part, we note that we can limit the expected time spent between the first solution in a phase being constructed, and the first decision stage of that phase, to lower order terms [29]. Since the number of periods is smaller than the number of phases, we can apply a similar reasoning to limit the contribution of such time between periods to a lower-order term.

Therefore, we see that FG is at least as fast as GRG, up to lower-order terms. Since GRG with the heuristic set of size k achieves the optimal runtime for LEADINGONES for the selected range of parameter values for τ , we can therefore state that FG also achieves optimal expected runtime for LEADINGONES with the heuristic set of size k , and the expected runtime stated in Theorem 12 in [29] also holds for FG. \square